

**EFFECTIVE WAYS OF CONDUCTING MASTER-STUDENT
TRADITIONS IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS**

Egamberdiyev Oyatillokh Alisher ugli

Fergana State University pedagogy - Psychology 4th year student of the faculty

Makhamadjonov Jakhongir Zakirjan ugli

Fergana State University pedagogy - Psychology 2nd year student of the faculty

Sobirova Azizaxon Maribjon kizi

Fergana State University pedagogy - Psychology 2nd year student of the faculty

Abstract: It is known that the experience of the teacher-student tradition, which has an educational impact on future specialist teachers in higher educational institutions, is expressed as a practically proven factor. As a result of the implementation of the process of scientific and technical development at a rapid pace, the professional relevance of specialists in such cases as the fact that the aspects of the educational process are perfecting, new pedagogical technologies, innovative methods are introduced into their system in a wide range, makes it necessary to focus on such issues as identifying issues, On its basis, the issues of educating a comprehensively developed harmonious generation were expressed. In the article, opinion and reflection will be made about the effective way to lead teacher-apprenticeship tradition in higher education institution.

Keywords: higher educational institutions, teacher – student traditions, effective methods, co-operation, development, interactive methods

Today, attention to the comprehensive formation of young specialists has always turned to the demand of the times for the need for relative acceleration, aimed at increasing their professional activity. The forms of bringing the experience gained in terms of changes in historical conditions to the minds of young people are also changing. Thanks to independence, one of the main tasks

of the further development of the teacher-student tradition is the establishment of a new education system that will form the basis for the development of independent Uzbekistan. The law “on education” and the national program for training personnel, adopted at the IX session of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on August 29, 1997, serve as the legal basis for its implementation.

Even today, the traditions of teacher-apprenticeship are used in many labor communities, including government agencies. However, at present, the reforms carried out in personnel policy require the implementation of mentoring in a formal and professional manner.

There are laws that are not written in life, but which, if not followed, lead to ugly consequences. One of these is the relationship of teacher and apprenticeship. Teacher and apprenticeship etiquette, value, conditions of communication among the people have lived and matured for millions of years in the form of such unwritten laws and are developing. There is no man of any profession that he has not matured in the sight of a master. The bond of Master and apprenticeship is very delicate, and if a slight rustle is tried, it can break off, and then a knot can remain even when connected. So that this does not happen, first of all, the disciple is obliged to give his teacher infinite love, trust, understand his every word, behavior, follow it. It is also customary for an apprentice to take his blessing, agreeing with his teacher before starting an independent work, to finish what he has learned from his teacher. And the disciples who did not receive a blessing did not have a pale Cup, and one did not have two. Obtaining consent is to ensure the improvement of the heart. Only a master who is full of joy from his disciple will give him a sincere blessing. Our people did not in vain weave the wise phrase “the disciple whom the teacher did not see - guides to every status.”

It is required that the apprentice, under the guidance of a teacher, carefully observes each of his actions and work methods, even cases of where to put what,

to which side to pay more attention, in the process of studying knowledge or craft. Usually the master sometimes does not even say every elixir of the craft, but shows it in practice. Maybe with this the teacher wants to test the vigilance, curiosity and interest of his student? The lover of a student who successfully passed this test will undoubtedly be a cherry.

It is worth saying that the most difficult among the man-made or crafts are the study of science, while absolutely not belittling other professions. The choice of a mentor in this regard is also of great importance. First of all, the teacher and the disciple must be worthy of each other, understand each other. In doing so, more responsibility falls on The Apprentice. Because an apprentice is obliged to Avay his teacher, put his respect in place, endure some of his whims, withstand such a painstaking work as digging a well with a needle.

Mentoring is a direction in the comprehensive education of young people. But this tradition is expressed as a continuation of the educational and educational influences of social institutions engaged in the education of young people of various content, such as Family, School. That is why cooperation with the activities of such teams as the family, school is carried out in the master-apprenticeship activities, and the forces of each other's influence are strengthened. Confirmation of the experience of social life confirms the future socio-political activity of mankind, the implementation of education on the basis of the delivery of education from generation to generation. Such high-level approvals also express the need for a high level of assessment of mentoring activities.

The activity of the teachers is to establish in the students that time indicators are carried out on a general state scale. And in the process, when solving the question of how to distribute Time, Master's instructions have a key place. Being able to attract students to acquire knowledge, skills in the direction of leisure by teaching them how to use goals, tasks, tools in any time distribution makes the figure of the teacher again a person of authority. It should also be

noted that the basis of this activity will not have any educational and educational value if only the material and economic side of the teacher-apprenticeship tradition is paid attention to.

In conclusion, on the basis of this activity, along with the principle of voluntariness, it is also expressed in the fact that systematically, in the content of cooperation, both sides raise the level of specialization to a higher level. Together with the characteristics of a high level of general specialization, the levels of cultural communication, attitude also develop and form. That is, in order to comprehensively form a future specialist according to the opinions of his great thinkers, the requirements that it is necessary to know him in every possible way as well as himself are made on the basis of the traditions of the “master disciple”.

References:

1. Azizkhadjjev N.N. Pedagogical technology and pedagogical skills. - Tashkent: TDPU, 2003. - 174 -p
2. Zaripav K.Z. Methodological research of the system of professional development of pedagogical Personnel // Public Education. - T.: 2003. 15.p
3. Zunnunov A, In Prisoner O. Didactics (theory of Education). For students of higher educational institutions – t. East, 2006. – 125.p
4. Moslimav N.A. Problems of a systematic approach to pedagogical activity // vocational education. – 2004. – № 3. - 24.p
5. <http://nafisa-4mak.zn.uz/dars-ishlanmalari/innovatsiyalar/ustoz-shogird/>